

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Reaction between Iodine and Nitrobenzene in Presence of Pyridine as a Halogen Carrier

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Kinetics of the reaction between iodine and nitrobenzene have been studied at various temperatures in presence of pyridine as a carrier. The I.R. of the reaction mixture has also been studied. The rate of the reaction has been followed by conductance measurements at different concentrations of the reactants. The reaction has been found to be first order with respect to iodine and first order with respect to nitrobenzene and is independent to pyridine concentration. Arrhenius parameters have been determined. The energy of activation is of the order of 9.6 ± 0.1 K.cal. The frequency factor is $2.2 \pm 0.1 \times 10^3$. I.R. result confirms that (m) $C_6H_4INO_2$ is formed as a product. The proposed mechanism of the reaction is :

Pyridine has been used as a halogen carrier^{1,2} in several reactions. Formation of pyridinium iodide complex in a mixture of pyridine and iodine has also been investigated by various workers³⁻⁶. In the present investigation the kinetics of iodination of nitrobenzene in presence of pyridine as a carrier has been studied at various temperatures and the I.R. of the product has also been studied with a view to find out the order of the reaction and also the mechanism of the reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials : B.D.H. (AnalaR) Samples of pyridine, nitrobenzene and resublimed Iodine (May and Baker) were used for the experiments. Pyridine and nitrobenzene were kept over caustic potash for several days and distilled. Iodine (AnalaR) was further purified by sublimation.

Apparatus : The apparatus used to measure the resistance was a combination of a-c bridge with a cathode ray oscilloscope⁵. Reaction was carried out in a thermostat with an accuracy of $\pm 0.01^\circ$. Glass stoppered Pyrex glass conductivity cell with vertical

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platinum electrodes were employed for the measurement of resistance. The electrodes were slightly platinized to get sharp null point. Platinised platinum had no effect on the individual reactants.

Solution I : A solution of iodine in nitrobenzene (10 ml. of 0.2*M*) was first prepared and was kept in the thermostat and it to 10 ml. of pyridine, which was also kept in thermostat, was added. The concentration of Iodine was 0.1*M* in the final mixture.

Solution II : A solution of iodine in pyridine (10 ml. of 0.2*M*) was first prepared and to it 10 ml. of nitrobenzene was added after the solution had attained the temperature of the bath. The final concentration of iodine in this case was also 0.1*M*.

Solution III : A mixture of pyridine and nitrobenzene (20 ml. by taking 10 ml. of each) was first prepared and then 0.1*M* of iodine solution was prepared in that mixture where the ratio of nitrobenzene to pyridine was 1 : 1.

Solution IV : A solution of Iodine was also prepared (0.1*M*) in the mixture of nitrobenzene and pyridine in the ratio of 2 : 1.

Solution V : A solution of iodine was prepared (0.1*M*) in the mixture containing nitrobenzene and pyridine in the ratio of 3 : 1.

The rate of the reaction was also followed by changing pyridine concentration, in the mixture keeping iodine concentration same in the mixture.

The rate of the reaction was followed in each case by the change in resistance with time. In order to find R_{00} the solutions were kept separately in glass stoppered bottles for several days and the resistance was measured in each case at the particular temperature at which the reaction was carried out from time to time till it was constant. To know the resistance at t_0 the extrapolation method was used. This was obtained by plotting a graph of resistance with time and then extrapolating to zero time.

For calculating specific reaction rate constant for the first order reaction, the following formula² was used.

$$k = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x} = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{R_t(R_{00}-R_0)}{(R_{00}-R_t)R_0}$$

where R = resistance at time ' t '; R_0 = resistance at zero time; R_{00} = equilibrium resistance.

Although iodine and pyridine react with each other, yet their rate of the reaction is very slow as compared with the present reaction. Therefore the change in resistance of solution of iodine in pyridine has been neglected in calculating the rate constant of the reaction. The values of the rate constant are given in Table 1.

Arrhenius plot is given in Fig. I. The I.R. of the reaction product was taken by Beckmann double beam I.R. spectrophotometer (see Fig. II) and the peak at 520 cm^{-1} confirms a (C-I) bond stretching in the product.

TABLE I
 Values of $K \times 10^5$ in min.^{-1}

Temp. in °C	Sol. I	Sol. II	Sol. III	Sol. IV	Sol. V
25	19.48	18.28	16.84	76.90	122.70
30	25.28	22.98	20.40	100.61	158.02
35	33.07	29.75	27.40	132.11	206.57
45	53.49	48.42	44.64	209.08	324.10
55	86.40	78.50	72.51	338.18	526.01

DISCUSSION

It is interesting to note that while following the rate of reaction by change in resistance with time, it was observed that although the overall concentration of the reactants in case of solution I, II and III are same, yet the resistance at the beginning of the reaction in case of solution I is comparatively less than in case of solution II and III. If the solutions are kept for a long time so that the resistance attains a constant value then the constant value of the resistance in each case is same. This was further checked by refluxing the three

solutions separately and then measuring the resistances. Resistances were found to be equal after reflux. This shows that the same mechanism is followed in each case. But since the solutions are prepared in those three different (I, II & III) ways probably the degree of ionisation of the complex (*Ibid*^{3,4}) immediately formed, is more in first case, than in the second and third solutions as a result of which the conductance in case of solution I is more at the beginning. The equilibrium of the complex $C_6H_5NI_2 \rightleftharpoons C_6H_5NI^+ + I^-$, is more towards the right side in the first case than in the second and third solution.

Variation of Reaction rates :

(a) From table 1 it can be seen that in case of solution I, II and III the reaction is first order with respect to iodine, the concentration of other reactants being very high.

(b) But in the case of solution IV and V, the rate constants increase gradually with the increasing proportion of nitrobenzene. This indicates that the rate constant is dependent on nitrobenzene concentration.

(c) When the pyridine concentration is changed keeping iodine concentration same in the mixture the specific reaction rate constant is not changed. This shows that the overall reaction is not dependent on pyridine concentration.

Therefore, it is most reasonable to predict that the reaction is first order with respect to iodine as well as nitrobenzene.

Constancy of Energy of activation : From Fig. I, it can be seen that the energy of activation is almost same in all cases, and is of the order of 9.6 k.cal. This indicates that same mechanism is followed in each case of solution I to V by changing pyridine and nitrobenzene proportion keeping iodine concentration same.

TABLE 2
*Values of log PZ and ΔS^**

Solutions	log PZ (min. ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (E.U.)
I	3.38	-35.14
II	3.37	-35.19
III	3.34	-35.33
IV	3.88	-32.84
V	4.19	-31.32

Constancy of the frequency factor : From table 2, it is observed that the values of 'A' are constant and are comparatively low. This can be explained by the effect of probability factor 'P' from the equations⁷,

$$P = (f_v/f_r)^5$$

and

$$Z = \left(k \frac{T}{h} \right) (f_r^2 / f_t^3)$$

Since the complexity of the reacting molecules increases with the solvation, in the present case, 'P' will have lower values and consequently 'A' factor will be low and the activated complex involves release of the energy of solvation, which will lower the activation energy. The lower value of 'E' and the lower value of 'P' will tend to compensate one another to some extent.

Entropy of activation (ΔS^):* ΔS^* has been calculated from the rate data using a standard equation :

$$K_r = (K T/h) e^{\Delta S^*/R} e^{-E_0/RT}$$

and

$$K_r = PZ e^{-E_0/RT}$$

so

$$PZ = (KT/h) e^{\Delta S^*/R}$$

If $10^{13} e^{-E_0/RT}$ is taken as a 'normal' value of a unimolecular rate constant⁷, then since $KT/h = 10^{13} \text{ Sec.}^{-1}$; $e^{\Delta S^*/R}$ is a factor which determines whether the reaction goes faster or slower than normal. If ΔS^* is positive, corresponding to a more probable activated complex, then the reaction is faster than normal. If ΔS^* is negative, the activated complex is less stable and the rate is slower.

When in the present work, the values of ΔS^* , are studied from Table 2, it is concluded that negative values of ΔS^* , probably are due to the fact that, in all cases of this reaction, the rate is comparatively slower than normal and the activated complex :

is relatively more unstable in the course of the reaction, leading to final product. In all the cases of solution I to V, the ΔS^* values are almost same.

I.R. spectrum shows a C-I bond stretching at 520 cm^{-1} which confirms that iodination of nitrobenzene takes place after iodine is ionised by pyridine. The halogenation of pyridine⁸ is not possible at the temperature of present study. It is only possible at high temperature. Therefore the mechanism of the reaction suggested is :

Step (1) is very slow as has been studied by several workers (*ibid*^{3,4}). Step (2) is spontaneous as it is an ionisation process, hence step (3) is the rate determining step of the reaction and pyridine acts as a halogen carrier.

R E F E R E N C E S

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